

ID	Título	Ano
EP1	Open Innovation Readiness Assessment within Students in Poland: Investigating State-of-the-Art and Challenges	2022
EP2	Universities in an open innovation system: a UK perspective	2012
EP3	Open innovation in universities: What motivates researchers to engage in knowledge transfer exchanges?	2012
EP4	University–industry relationships and open innovation: Towards a research agenda	2007
EP5	Os sistemas nacional e regional de inovação e sua influência na interação universidade-empresa em Santa Catarina	2016
EP6	University-industry knowledge exchange: An exploratory study of Open Innovation in UK universities	2015
EP7	Shifting sands: Regional perspectives on the role of social capital in supporting open innovation through knowledge transfer and exchange with small and medium-sized enterprises	2012
EP8	Managing Strategic Partnerships with Universities in Innovation Ecosystems: A Research Agenda	2018
EP9	How Doctoral Students and Graduates Can Facilitate Boundary Spanning between Academia and Industry	2018
EP10	Achieving Innovation and Entrepreneurship by Applying Education 4.0 and Open Innovation	2020
EP11	Barriers to Applying Open Innovation at Universities	2011
EP12	Does Open Innovation Promote Innovation Efficiency in Chinese Universities?	2022
EP13	Enhancing Technology-Focused Entrepreneurship in Higher Education Institutions Ecosystem: Implementing Innovation Models in International Projects	2024
EP14	Open Collaborative Innovation in the Context of OER	2014
EP15	Open Innovation Laboratory: Education 4.0 Environments to improve competencies in scholars	2020
EP16	Open Innovation Strategies in Engineering Education	2023
EP17	Open Innovation with Value Co-Creation from University–Industry Collaboration	2022
EP18	Experiences in Interactive Collaborative Learning using an Open Innovation Laboratory: The Design Methodologies Course as Case Study	2022
EP19	Fundamental elements of university-industry interaction from a grounded theory approach	2012
EP20	Innovation Through Collaboration: Company-University Partnership Strategies	2012
EP21	Integrating the Crowd Through Social Media: How Higher Education Can Profit from Viral Mechanisms	2007
EP22	Internal and External Coordinated Open Innovation Ecosystems: Concept Building and Applying to Shanghai Zizhu International Education Park	2016
EP23	Open Innovation Capacity of the Polish Universities	2015
EP24	Open Innovation Community for University–Industry Knowledge Transfer: A Colombian Case	2012
EP25	Open innovation concept: integrating universities and business in digital age	2018
EP26	Open Innovation for Course Development Process Using Simulation-based Programming	2018
EP27	Open Innovation Laboratories as Enabling Resources to Reach the Vision of Education 4.0	2020
EP28	Open Innovation Laboratory for Rapid Realization of Sensing, Smart and Sustainable Products (S3 Products) for Higher Education	2011
EP29	Open innovation laboratory in electrical energy education based on the knowledge economy	2022
EP30	Promotion of university students' collaborative skills in open innovation environment	2024
EP31	Student customized creative education model based on open innovation	2014
EP32	The challenges facing corporate universities in dealing with open innovation	2020
EP33	The Opportunity in Higher Education: how open education and peer-to-peer networks are essential for higher education	2023
EP34	Together We are Less Alone - A Concept for a Regional Open Innovation Learning Lab	2022
EP35	Training Entrepreneurial Competences with Open Innovation Paradigm in Higher Education	2019

Legenda: [EP#]: ID do Estudo Primário